

Energy Flow: Fusion in Stars

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Abstract

Nuclear fusion, powered by the interaction of fundamental particles and forces, is the energy source of stars. This paper will explain how energy is stored, transferred, and released through fusion processes. We will analyze fusion's role in the formation of heavier elements and the release of large amounts of energy. By understanding the processes involved in fusion, we will gain insight into the evolution of stars and fusion's role in shaping the universe. We will also learn how better understanding stellar fusion could potentially impact us in the future.

Introduction

Stars are, in essence, self-sustaining fusion reactors. They are an excellent example of how energy is stored in the nuclei of atoms. Through fusion, stars convert lighter elements into heavier ones, releasing energy in the form of light and heat. This paper will explore the flow of energy in stars, the mechanisms of fusion, and how energy is stored, transferred, and lost through different stages of stellar evolution.

Fusion in Main Sequence Stars

Main sequence stars generate energy through the proton-proton chain reaction, fusing hydrogen into helium. Two protons fuse, forming deuterium and releasing a positron and a neutrino. The deuterium then fuses with another proton to form helium-3 and releases gamma radiation. Two helium-3 nuclei then collide and fuse, creating helium-4 and releasing two protons. (Britannica 2023). This process involves the interactions between quarks and the strong nuclear force.

Protons and neutrons are made of quarks held together by the strong nuclear force, derived from gluons. During fusion, protons collide at high speeds. Because protons are positively charged, they repel each other due to the electromagnetic force. An exception to this occurs during extremely high temperatures, such as millions of degrees Fahrenheit, where the protons have enough kinetic energy to overcome the repulsion of the electromagnetic force and come close enough together for the strong nuclear force to combine them together (Barbarino 2023).

Energy Storage

Energy is stored in the form of mass within protons and neutrons as seen in Einstein's famous equation $E=mc^2$. When hydrogen nuclei fuse to form helium, some mass is lost in the process. This mass is converted into energy which is released as heat and light from the star. This is the reason why stellar fusion releases massive amounts of energy (Britannica 2023).

Energy Loss

Energy is lost during stellar fusion through the emission of photons and neutrinos. The emission of photons results in light radiation which escapes from the surface of the star. Stellar fusion also results in the release of neutrinos, which leave the sun and travel through space. These neutrinos carry away some of the energy released from fusion (PSU).

The Role of Fundamental Forces in Stellar Fusion

i. Gravitational Force

Gravity causes matter to collapse inward. This causes high temperatures and pressure in the core of stars which allow fusion to occur. Gravity along with fusion forms hydrostatic equilibrium which causes the formation of a star.

ii. Electromagnetic Force

Electromagnetic force governs the repulsion between protons due to their like charges. Overcoming this repulsion requires extremely high temperatures, which give the protons the necessary kinetic energy to collide and fuse together.

iii. Strong Nuclear Force

During extremely high temperatures when protons are colliding together, the strong nuclear force allows the protons to overcome the electromagnetic force, allowing them to stick together. This results in the fusion of lighter elements into heavier ones (UEN).

iv. Weak Nuclear Force

During the proton-proton chain reaction, one of the protons is converted into a neutron through a weak nuclear interaction, producing a positron and a neutrino (Britannica 2023).

Supernova Energy Release

In the last stages of a star's life, the star stops fusion when the star's core accumulates lots of iron, as fusing iron requires energy to be input instead of releasing it. Due to the termination of fusion, gravity causes the star to collapse in on itself with little opposition. The collapse of the core of the star causes a rapid buildup of pressure and heat and, in a high-mass star, results in a supernova. This increased density and temperature in the core causes two things to happen. First, gamma rays are produced which can split iron nuclei into alpha particles, free protons, and free neutrons. Second, it allows for electron capture. In the electron capture, an electron and a proton change into a neutron and an electrical neutrino. The core of the star continues to collapse until it reaches a point where neutron degeneracy pressure becomes strong enough to halt the collapse. This state is known as a neutron star (Timlin). Even though the core cannot collapse any further, the outer layers of the star are still falling towards the core due to gravity. Once the outer layers hit the dense core, a shockwave is formed. The powerful shockwave formed by this collision

moves is known as a supernova. The supernova explosion releases tons of energy, which mainly stems from the release of neutrinos (Liland). The supernova's shockwave causes fusion to occur in the outer shell as it heats the outer layers to very high temperatures. Nucleosynthesis occurs and the fusion reactions create new atomic nuclei (DOE).

Sequence of Supernova

1. **Iron Accumulation:** Iron accumulates in the core
2. **Core Collapse:** When the core is mostly made of iron fusion stops. This is because fusing iron requires energy input instead of releasing energy. Due to the halt of fusion, gravity causes the star to collapse in on itself. This causes the star to condense, creating massive amounts of pressure and heat in the core.
3. **Gamma Ray Production:** Due to the high temperature and density of the core, gamma rays are produced. These gamma rays split iron nuclei into alpha particles, free protons, and free neutrons.
4. **Electron Capture:** Electrons and protons in the core combine, forming neutrons. This process releases neutrinos.
5. **Shockwave Triggered by Neutron Star Formation:** The core of the star collapses until it becomes a neutron star. When the falling outer layers of the star impact the neutron star, a violent shockwave is released.
6. **Supernova Explosion:** The supernova explosion due to the immense pressure and heat in the core, releases tons of energy in the form of neutrinos. The shockwave from the supernova heats the outer layers of the former star, causing a series of fusion reactions that result in the formation of heavier elements.

Societal Impact

Understanding how stars produce energy through fusion can improve our understanding of fusion and can allow us to, one day in the far future, utilize fusion energy on Earth. The ability to harness fusion energy would drastically increase global energy production, and reduce our reliance on fossil fuels.

Environmental Impact

Fusion in stars generates elements that are essential to life. They also contribute to the formation and deposition of heavy elements across the universe. Additionally, if we are able to, one day, harness fusion energy and use it on Earth, we can reduce our reliance on fossil fuels, helping reduce climate change.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the process of stellar fusion demonstrates the power of the fundamental forces. It allows lighter elements to be fused into heavier ones, and it causes the generation of massive amounts of energy. The energy produced by fusion in these stars helps drive the processes of the universe. By understanding stellar fusion and the forces involved, we can learn how to potentially harness fusion energy and utilize it here on Earth. A good area to strengthen research is the development of new materials that can withstand the extreme heat of a fusion reactor. The development of these materials could help open doorways to the use of fusion energy on Earth. If we are able to develop a material that can withstand the extreme temperatures of fusion, we will be one step closer to utilizing fusion energy on Earth as a sustainable, clean energy source.

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